

Navigating Chronic Illness Care Amidst a Global Pandemic: Insights from Missed Clinic Visits Before, During and After COVID-19 in Nigeria

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Abstract

Background: Anti-pandemic tactics impacted global healthcare service delivery, reducing access to routine treatment in clinics. This study looked at the frequency of missed outpatient clinic visits before, during, and after the COVID-19 pandemic, as well as the factors that influenced them among patients with chronic conditions.

Methods: A hospital-based cross-sectional study was undertaken on 400 patients with chronic conditions who attended outpatient clinics at the University of Ilorin Teaching Hospital in Ilorin, Nigeria. A pretested interviewer-administered semi-structured questionnaire was used to collect data, which was then analysed using IBM's Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) software version 21. Descriptive and inferential statistics were used.

Results: In 2020, 269 (67.3%) of respondents skipped at least one clinic appointment, up from 126 (31.5%) before COVID-19 (2019) and 122 (30.5%) after COVID-19 in 2021. COVID-19 restrictions prevented more than four-fifths (88.0%) of responders from attending clinic appointments. Other factors that increased the rate of missed clinic visits included patients who were not accompanied to the clinic ($p=0.002$), those who were not consistent with their medications ($p=0.005$), those who lived outside town ($p=0.017$), those who attended more than one clinic ($p=0.015$), and patients who had more than one chronic disease ($p=0.040$).

Conclusion: Patients with chronic illnesses who attended follow-up clinics missed significantly more clinic sessions in 2020 (during the peak of the COVID-19 epidemic) compared to previous and subsequent years. It is advised that telemedicine and other technical breakthroughs be used as treatment methods to avoid this in the future.

Keywords: Missed clinic visits, COVID-19, Chronically ill patients, Nigeria

Introduction

Infectious illness emergence and re-emergence have grown more common worldwide, owing to causes such as human growth, demographics, population

dynamics, and environmental change (1,2). The COVID-19 pandemic, which was caused by the new coronavirus SARS-CoV-2, is one of the most severe health catastrophes in recent memory. COVID-19 began in Wuhan, China, in December 2019, and

quickly spread to pandemic status, significantly altering attitudes on global health, safety, and healthcare-seeking behaviors (3,4).

The pandemic reaction, which included broad lockdown measures, had a significant impact on ordinary healthcare services around the world, particularly for people with chronic conditions. The repercussions of such interruptions are particularly concerning in low- and middle-income countries (LMICs) such as Nigeria, where healthcare disparities are stark. Studies have found a decrease in healthcare utilization during the pandemic, which has important implications for chronic illness management (5-9).

According to available data, the increase in COVID-19 cases during the early pandemic was accompanied by a decrease in non-COVID-19 hospital admissions and clinic visits as the population's health-seeking behavior declined (10, 11). A research in Addis Ababa revealed significant disruptions in healthcare services during the COVID-19 pandemic (12). According to an HIV care study, the top reason people did not visit healthcare facilities during the lockdown period was fear of developing COVID-19 (13). In Rwanda, 44% of patients reported at least one impediment to obtaining healthcare during the COVID-19 lockdown.⁷ A study in China found that healthcare use had plummeted by 40.8% (14).

Despite accumulating evidence of the pandemic's impact on healthcare-seeking behaviours, there is a scarcity of studies explicitly investigating missed outpatient clinic visits among chronic illness patients across the various stages of the COVID-19 pandemic. Understanding these patterns and their related characteristics is critical for shaping future epidemic response tactics and meeting the requirements of chronic illness patients during times of limited healthcare access (15). This study looked into missed clinic visits before, during, and after the COVID-19 epidemic, as well as the reasons that contributed to them, among patients with chronic conditions who visited consultants' outpatient clinics at a Nigerian tertiary health center.

Methodology

Study Area

University of Ilorin Teaching Hospital (UIITH) is a federal tertiary hospital in Kwara state's capital city, Ilorin, Nigeria. It provides all levels of care to patients in Kwara and neighboring states such as Kogi, Osun, Oyo, and Niger states. It has 650 beds and receives an average of 1,000 in-patients per month. The hospital has 21 outpatient clinics, excluding those dedicated to pediatric treatment.

These clinics are open on various days of the week. In 2018, 2019, and 2020, these outpatient clinics saw around 6152, 7955, and 3322 patients.

Study design

The study is a hospital-based cross-sectional study of patients with chronic diseases who frequent outpatient clinics at the University of Ilorin Teaching Hospital (UIITH) in Ilorin, Nigeria.

Study Population

Patients with chronic diseases attending outpatient clinics at UIITH, Ilorin. Patients under the age of 18, those who had not begun visiting clinic by December 2018, and those who did not require follow-up visits were excluded from the study.

Sample size and technique

The sample size was estimated using Leslie Fischer's approach, with a standard deviation at the 95% confidence interval (1.96) and a p-value of 44% (7). The minimum sample size computed was 379. For a population of fewer than 10,000, the projected sample size was 356. With a 10% non-response rate, the required sample size increased to 396. However, the study had a total of 400 respondents (Figure 1). The study participants were selected from outpatient clinics using a multistage sampling procedure.

Data collection

Data was collected from November 23rd, 2022 to January 13th, 2023, utilizing an interviewer-administered semi-structured questionnaire and the KoboCollect app (<https://ee.kobotoolbox.org/x/TQhWSPQf>). To verify the tool, a pretest study was conducted with forty respondents from a specialty outpatient clinic at General Hospital in Ilorin, Nigeria; the Cronbach's alpha for the pretest was 0.816, showing extremely strong reliability. Four trained research assistants collected information from participants. The research assistants were postgraduate medical students pursuing residency training in public health who were trained by the primary investigator. Prior to the start of the study, three physical training sessions were held in which issues concerning data collection, confidentiality, and respondent autonomy were discussed; additionally, role play was conducted among the research assistants to simulate how the questionnaire would be administered on the field.

Figure 1. Flowchart for sampling

Table 1. Socio-demographic characteristics of respondents

Socio-demographic Characteristics	Frequency (n=400)	Percentage	
Age (years) <35 35-44 45-54 55-64 65-74 >74 Mean age ($\pm$SD) Minimum age Maximum age	14 36 91 107 102 50	3.5% 9.0% 22.8% 26.8% 25.5% 12.5%	59 (13.1) 20 95
Sex Female Male	225 175	56.2% 43.8%	
Marital Status Single Married Widowed Divorced/Separated	7 330 60 3	1.8% 82.5% 15.0% 0.7%	
Type of marriage Monogamy Polygamy	(n=330) 251 79	83.7% 26.3%	
Educational Status None Primary Secondary Tertiary	46 37 112 205	11.5% 9.3% 28.0% 51.2%	
Employment Status Employed Self-employed Unemployed	153 132 115	38.3% 33.0% 28.7%	
Monthly Income (Naira) <50000 50000-100000 100001-150000 150001-200000 >200000 Median (IQR)	170 141 46 24 19	42.5% 35.3% 11.5% 6.0% 4.7%	54,500.0 (70,000.0)
Place of Residence Outside Ilorin Within Ilorin	54 346	13.5% 86.5%	
The usual mode of transportation to UITH Own car Family member/relative Public transport Personal Motorcycle	102 80 216 2	25.5% 20.0% 54.0% 0.5%	
Accompany to the clinic Accompanied Not accompanied	162 238	40.5% 59.5%	

Table 2. Clinic details of the respondents

Variable	Frequency (n=400)	Percentage	
Number of various outpatient clinics usually attended	308	77.0%	1.3 (0.6)
1	79	19.8%	
2	9	2.2%	
3	2	0.5%	
4	2	0.5%	
5			
Mean (±SD)			
Clinic most often attended			
Cardiology	103	25.8%	
Endocrinology	95	23.8%	
Gastroenterology	28	7.0%	
General surgery	27	6.7%	
Nephrology	11	2.7%	
Neurology	57	14.2%	
Neurosurgery	7	1.8%	
Orthopaedic	35	8.8%	
Plastic surgery	4	1.0%	
Urology	25	6.2%	
Others	8	2.0%	
Number of chronic diseases			
1	272	68.0%	1.4 (0.6)
2	111	27.7%	
3	15	3.8%	
4	2	0.5%	
Mean (±SD)			
Number of years since the clinic visit started			
<6	197	49.3%	7.3 (5.1)
6-10	130	32.5%	
11-15	48	12.0%	
16-20	17	4.2%	
>20	8	2.0%	
Mean (±SD)			

Table 3. Health Seeking Behaviour, source and use of medication by patients before, during and after COVID 19 Pandemic (2019, 2020, 2021)

Variable	2019 n (%)	2020 n (%)	2021 n (%)
Number of clinics attended Mean ($\pm$SD)	5.8 (3.4)	2.7 (3.1)	5.2 (3.5)
Miss any clinic appointments Yes	126 (31.5)	269 (67.3)	122 (30.5)
Visit another place for healthcare as a result missing clinic appointment	(n=126)	(n=269)	(n=122)
Yes	51 (40.5)	121 (45.0)	49 (40.2)
Health facility visited	(n=51)	(n=121)	(n=49)
Church/Mosque	0 (0.0)	2 (1.7)	1 (2.0)
Government Hospital	7 (13.8)	9 (7.4)	10 (20.4)
Patent Medicine Store	15 (29.4)	38 (31.4)	12 (24.6)
Private Clinic	21 (41.2)	56 (46.3)	24 (49.0)
Traditional Healer	4 (7.8)	5 (4.1)	1 (2.0)
Others	4 (7.8)	11 (9.1)	1 (2.0)
Medications source			
Church/Mosque	0 (0.0)	2 (0.5)	0 (0.0)
Government Hospital	269 (67.2)	171 (42.8)	270 (67.5)
Nowhere	2 (0.5)	9 (2.2)	3 (0.8)
Patent Medicine Store	10 (2.5)	62 (15.5)	15 (3.7)
Pharmacy	115 (28.8)	131 (32.7)	106 (26.5)
Private Clinic	2 (0.5)	20 (5.0)	6 (1.5)
Traditional Healer	0 (0.0)	5 (1.3)	5 (0.0)
Others	2 (0.5)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)
Regular on medication Yes	377 (94.2)	361 (90.2)	380 (95.0)
Reason for not being regular on medication	(n=23)	(n=39)	(n=20)
Could not afford it	6 (26.1)	9 (23.1)	10 (50.0)
Not available	0 (0.0)	2 (5.1)	1 (5.0)
Pill burden	0 (0.0)	1 (2.6)	0 (0.0)
Tired of taking medication	0 (0.0)	4 (10.3)	2 (10.0)
Unable to get to UITH	2 (8.7)	13 (33.3)	1 (5.0)
Not on medications	9 (39.1)	10 (25.6)	6 (30.0)

Table 4. Missed clinic visit during COVID-19 lock down

Variable	Frequency (n=400)	Percentage	
Had difficulty in attending clinic			
Yes	239	59.8%	
Miss any appointment due to lockdown			
Yes	270	67.5%	
Number of appointments missed	(n=270)		
1	56	20.7%	
2	35	13.0%	
3	43	15.9%	
4	28	10.4%	
5	24	8.9%	
6-10	63	23.3%	
>10	21	7.8%	
Mean (±SD)			4.5 (3.7)
Most common reason for missing appointment	(n=270)		
Fear of being infected with COVID-19			
No money	75	27.8%	
No movement			
No transportation	1	0.4%	
Not attended to at the clinic	135	50.0%	
^a Others	18	6.7%	
	32	11.8%	
	9	3.3%	
Visited UITH clinic during the pandemic without being attended to			
Yes	29	7.2%	
Visited another healthcare provider as a result of not going to your clinic in UITH during the lock down	(n=270)		
Yes	116	43.0%	
Facility visited	(n=116)		
Government Hospital	9	7.8%	
Patent Medicine Store	33	28.5%	
Private Clinic	60	51.7%	
Traditional Healer	2	1.7%	
^b Others	12	10.3%	
Medication source following missing appointment	(n=116)		
Government Hospital			
Patent Medicine Store	5	4.3%	
Private Clinic	45	38.8%	
Traditional Healer	21	18.1%	
Pharmacy	1	0.9%	
	44	37.9%	
Difficult to get to buy your medications during lockdown			
Yes	47	11.7%	

a Other reasons for missing appointments during lockdown are doctors on strike (1, 11.1%), patients advised not to come (1, 11.1%), the patient with children (1, 11.1%), forgetting appointments (1, 11.1%), out of town (2, 22.2%), patient feeling better (3, 33.3%).

b Other health facilities visited are private home doctor (1, 8.3%) and pharmacy (11, 91.6%)

Table 5a. Socio-demographic factors associated with clinic attendance before, during and after COVID-19 pandemic among respondents

	Before(2019)			During(2020)			After(2021)		
Socio-demographics	No Clinic Missed n=274 n(%)	Missed Clinic n=126 n(%)	p-value	No Clinic Missed n=131 n(%)	Missed Clinic n=269 n(%)	p-value	No Clinic Missed n=278 n(%)	Missed Clinic n=122 n(%)	p-value
Age (years)			0.111			0.092			0.001
<41	21 (7.7)	16 (10.7)		6 (5.6)	31 (11.5)		22 (8.0)	15 (12.3)	
41-50	50 (14.6)	29 (23.0)		17 (13.0)	52 (19.4)		35 (12.6)	34 (27.9)	
51-60	71(25.9)	32 (25.4)		41 (31.3)	62 (23.0)		74 (26.6)	29 (23.8)	
61-70	85 (31.0)	29 (23.0)		40 (30.5)	74 (27.5)		87 (31.2)	27 (22.1)	
>70	57 (20.8)	20 (15.9)		27 (20.6)	50 (18.6)		60 (21.6)	17 (13.9)	
Sex			0.807			0.477			0.067
Female	153 (55.8)	72 (57.1)		77 (58.8)	148 (55.0)		148 (53.2)	77 (63.1)	
Male	121 (44.2)	54 (42.9)		54 (41.2)	121 (45.0)		130 (46.8)	45 (36.9)	
Place of Residence			0.346			0.076			0.017
Outside Ilorin	34 (12.4)	20 (15.9)		12 (9.2)	42 (15.6)		30 (10.8)	24 (19.7)	
Within Ilorin	240 (87.6)	106 (84.1)		119 (90.8)	227 (84.4)		248 (89.2)	98 (80.3)	

Table 5b. Other factors associated with health-seeking behaviours before, during and after COVID-19 pandemic among respondents

Variable	Before (2019)			During (2020)			After (2021)		
	No Clinic Missed n=274 n(%)	Missed Clinic n=126 n(%)	p-value	No Clinic Missed n=131 n(%)	Missed Clinic n=269 n(%)	p-value	No Clinic Missed n=278 n(%)	Missed Clinic n=122 n(%)	p-value
Accompany to the clinic			0.002			0.052			0.101
Accompanied	125 (45.6)	37 (29.4)		62 (47.3)	100 (37.2)		120 (43.2)	42 (34.4)	
Not accompanied	149 (54.4)	89 (70.6)		69 (52.7)	169 (62.8)		158 (56.8)	80 (65.6)	
Number of regular outpatient clinic attended			0.134			0.795			0.015
1	216 (78.8)	92 (73.0)		98 (74.8)	210 (78.0)		220 (79.1)	88 (72.1%)	
2	52(19.0)	27 (21.4)		29 (22.1)	50 (18.6)		52 (18.8)	27 (22.1%)	
3	3 (1.1)	6 (4.8)		2 (1.5)	7 (2.6)		2 (0.7%)	7 (5.7%)	
4	2 (0.7)	0 (0.0)		1 (0.8)	1 (0.4)		2 (0.7%)	0 (0%)	
5	1 (0.4)	1 (0.8)		1 (0.8)	1 (0.4)		2 (0.7%)	0 (0%)	
Number of chronic diseases			0.129			0.720			0.040
1	193 (70.4)	79 (62.7)		89 (67.9)	183 (68.0)		196 (70.5)	76 (62.3)	
2	72 (26.3)	39 (31.0)		38 (29.0)	73 (27.2)		74 (26.6)	37 (30.3)	
3	7 (2.6)	8 (6.3)		4 (31.1)	11 (4.1)		6 (2.2)	9 (7.4)	
4	2 (0.7)	0 (0.0)		0 (0.0)	2 (0.7)		2 (0.7)	0 (0.0)	
Regular on medication			0.000			0.005			0.000
Yes	269 (98.2)	108 (85.7)		126 (96.2)	235 (87.4)		274 (95.6)	106 (86.9)	

Data Management

The analysis was carried out using version 21 of the IBM Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) software. Chi-square tests are used for descriptive and inferential statistics. Data was presented as frequency tables and charts. Significant levels were chosen at a p-value <0.05 at 95% confidence range..

Results

Table 1 displays the sociodemographic characteristics of the respondents. The study had 400 participants, with the median age group being 55-64 years, which accounted for 107 (26.8%) of them. The average age of responders was 59 ± 13.1 years. There were 225 female responders (56.2%), and 175 male respondents (43.8%). The bulk of the respondents, 330 (82.5%), were married, with 251 (83.7%) of the married respondents being in monogamous relationships.

As shown in table 1, about half of the respondents (51.2%) had tertiary education, and slightly more than one-third were gainfully employed (153, 38.3%). 170 (42.5%) of respondents had a monthly income of less than 50,000 naira, with a median of 54,500 naira and an interquartile range of 70,000 naira. The majority of responders (346, or 86.5%) lived in Ilorin. 216 (54.0%) of respondents used public transit to get to the hospital, and more than half, 238 (59.5%), arrived at the clinic alone.

Table 2 reveals that 308 respondents (77.0%) went to at least one clinic. The cardiology clinic had the most respondents (103, 25.8%), followed by the endocrinology clinic (95, 23.8%), while neurosurgery (7, 1.8%), and plastic surgery (4, 1.0%), had the fewest respondents. Two-thirds of the respondents, 272 (68.0%), had one chronic condition, and 111 (27.7%) had two. Approximately half of the respondents, 197 (49.3%), had been visiting the clinics for less than six years, while slightly less than one-third had been there for six to ten years. Only 8 (2.0%) patients had been visiting the clinic for more than 20 years, with an average annual visit of 7.3 ± 5.1 years.

Figure 1 shows that the cardiology clinic was the most commonly visited outpatient clinic in 2019. In 2021, however, nephrology clinics were the most popular. In 2020, clinic attendance was lowest across all clinics.

Figure 2 shows that in 2019, 2020, and 2021, respondents attended clinics an average of 5.8 ± 3.4 , 2.7 ± 3.1 , and 5.2 ± 3.5 times, respectively. In 2020, 269 (67.3%) of respondents skipped at least one clinic appointment, up from 126 (31.5%) before COVID-19 (2019) and 122 (30.5%) after COVID-19

in 2021. The largest average number of missed clinic appointments occurred in 2020 (4.6), while the averages for 2019 and 2021 were 2.8 and 3.4, respectively.

Figure 3 shows that COVID-19 limits were the most common reason respondents missed clinic appointments in 2020, accounting for more than four-fifths (88.0%).

Table 3 reveals that individuals aged 41 to 50 were more likely to miss clinic in 2021 ($p=0.01$). All other socio-demographic variables had no statistically significant link with clinic attendance in 2020 or 2021.

More than half of the responders, 239 (59.8%), had trouble getting to their clinics during the lockdown, with 67.5% missing their appointments. 63 (23.3%) responders missed 6-10 clinic appointments during the lockout, with a mean of 4.5 ± 3.7 . The primary reasons provided by respondents for skipping their clinics were a lack of movement in approximately half, 135 (50.0%), and a concern of contracting COVID-19 in more than a quarter, 75 (27.8%). Less than one-tenth of the respondents, 29 (7.2%), visited UITH during the lockdown but were not seen by a healthcare worker. More than half of the respondents, 154 (57%), did not seek alternative healthcare providers after missed appointments at UITH, while 60 (51.7%) saw other healthcare professionals in private clinics.

Table 4 shows that nearly half (45.0%) of those who missed their clinic visit went to another healthcare facility in 2020, compared to 40.5% and 40.2% before and after COVID-19, respectively. In 2019, 2020, and 2021, the majority of individuals who visited another health facility went to a private clinic (41.2 percent, 46.3%, and 49%). The biggest proportion of responders in 2019, 269 (67.2%), and in 2021, 270 (67.5%), were able to obtain their prescriptions from government hospitals, whereas just 171 (42.8%) did so during the peak of the epidemic in 2020. Almost all respondents reported taking their prescription on a regular basis (94.2% in 2019, 90.2% in 2020, and 95% in 2021). The most common reason why respondents who were not regular on meds did not use their drugs in 2019 was because they were not on medications, 9 (39.1%); in 2020, it was because they were unable to travel to UITH for it, 13 (33.3%); and in 2021, cost was the biggest obstacle, 10 (50%).

Table 5 shows that in 2019, those who were not accompanied to the clinic were more likely to miss their visit. ($p= 0.002$). Patients who took their drugs on a regular basis were less likely to miss their clinic appointments. ($p=0.000$). In 2020, there were no statistically significant relationships, with the exception that individuals who took their drugs on a

regular basis were less likely to miss their clinic visits. ($p=0.005$). In 2021, Ilorin residents were unlikely to miss their clinic visit. ($p=0.017$) Furthermore, those who visited more than one clinic ($p=0.015$) and had more than one chronic disease ($p=0.040$) were more likely to miss their clinic appointment. Patients who took their drugs on a regular basis were less likely to miss their clinic appointments. ($p=0.000$)

Discussion

The COVID-19 pandemic has taken a heavy toll on global healthcare systems, notably in the management of chronic illnesses, as seen in LMICs (16). This study focuses on patients who visit consultant clinics, a population with a high incidence of chronic conditions that necessitate regular follow-up visits. Throughout the epidemic, particularly during lockdowns, access to these critical healthcare services was severely limited. In this survey, more than two-thirds of respondents had one chronic condition, with the remaining one-third having several chronic illnesses. More than half of the respondents had been visiting the clinic for more than six years. The average number of clinic visits in 2019, 2020, and 2021 was 5.8 ± 3.4 , 2.7 ± 3.1 , and 5.2 ± 3.5 , respectively. In comparison to clinic appointments in 2019 and 2021, less than one-third missed at least one visit. In 2020, more than two-thirds of respondents missed at least one medical visit due to the COVID-19 shutdown. This was comparable to what was reported among people with chronic illnesses who visited follow-up clinics in Singapore and Ethiopia (17-19).

In 2020, when COVID-19 was at its pinnacle, the majority of persons who missed more than five clinic visits fell into this category, as opposed to previous and subsequent years. Data analysis showed a significant rise in missed clinic appointments during the pandemic's peak in 2020, with COVID-19 restrictions, fear of infection, and transportation issues reported as the top reasons. This is consistent with previous research, which found that fear of COVID-19 and transportation issues were the primary causes of poor health-seeking behavior among persons with chronic illnesses visiting follow-up clinics (18-20). Unlike affluent countries where telemedicine has made progress, Nigeria has yet to fully implement telemedicine as a therapeutic strategy. If implemented in Nigeria, it will greatly assist persons suffering from chronic conditions in receiving assistance during outbreaks that require movement restrictions (21).

Interestingly, despite worries about COVID-19 transmission, many patients sought alternative care,

primarily at private clinics and patent medicine stores, highlighting the ongoing need for healthcare access. This could be because individuals recognize that the research location, being the state's only tertiary health facility, may have more COVID-19 cases. Those who skipped clinic visits sought care elsewhere, especially at private clinics and patent medicine stores. This is hardly surprising given that these facilities are where individuals go when they are sick, serve as alternatives to public/government health facilities, and are frequently close to where the patients live. In contrast to our findings, an Ethiopian study found that for those who missed their clinic visits, the majority took no alternative activities, with one of the least alternative actions being to seek care in a private health facility (18).

This investigation also found that the medication was primarily sourced from the study site in 2019, 2020, and 2021. This could be due to people's assumption that hospital pharmaceuticals are superior to those obtained elsewhere, as well as their trust in the regular physicians who prescribe drugs to them. Despite the fact that the drugs were acquired from the study location, the proportion decreased in 2020 when compared to the years preceding and after. This may be due to COVID-19 limits. There was also a decrease in the frequency of medication intake in 2020 as compared to the previous and subsequent years. When compared to previous years, approximately one-third of individuals who reported they were not frequent medication users stated that they were unable to visit the hospital to acquire their meds due to COVID-19 restrictions. A study of people in certain Anglophone countries in West Africa found that those with chronic illnesses had restricted access to treatment and medicine supplies during the COVID-19 pandemic.²¹ The decrease in medication adherence and regular clinic attendance during the pandemic raises serious concerns about disease progression, consequences, and overall quality of life for chronic illness patients. While the research site remained the principal source of medication, supply and access disruptions underscore patients' vulnerability during periods of limited mobility (22-24).

The cardiology clinic was the most frequently attended by the study's respondents. This is also consistent with a research conducted in Ethiopia, where the cardiology clinic had the largest number of patients with chronic conditions (18). This is not surprising given that cardiovascular diseases are the most common types of chronic illnesses, and the burden of cardiovascular diseases is increasing in low- and middle-income countries (25).

In 2020, there were no statistically significant connections between characteristics evaluated and

missed clinics, with the exception that individuals who did not take their medications on a regular basis were more likely to skip their clinic visit ($p=0.000$). Before the COVID-19 lockdown in 2019, those who were not accompanied to the clinic were more likely to miss their clinic appointment ($p= 0.002$), while those who did not take their prescriptions on a regular basis were more likely to miss their clinic visit ($p=0.000$). In 2021, those who lived in the same city as the study location were unlikely to skip their clinic visit. ($p=0.017$). This was supported by the fact that the most prevalent cause for missing a clinic visit in 2021 was the great distance from their home to the healthcare institution. According to studies conducted in Oman (26) and India (27), one of the causes for missed clinic visits was the vast distance to the health institution. Furthermore, those who visited more than one clinic ($p=0.017$) and had more than one chronic disease ($p=0.040$) were more likely to miss their clinic appointment. This could be because patients with more than one chronic condition may have to visit multiple clinics, which can be a daunting process. This was also corroborated by a Singapore study that found that patients with chronic illnesses who had multiple appointments struggled with out-of-pocket expenses and travel logistics (28). Those who did not take their drugs on a regular basis were more likely to miss their clinic appointments ($p=0.000$). Non-adherence to medication was linked to missed clinic appointments in 2019, 2020, and 2021. This could be because clients who skipped clinics were unable to receive medicine refills. The link between missed clinic visits and criteria such as medication adherence, clinic attendance history, and geographical closeness to healthcare facilities highlights the intricate interplay of chronic illness patients' socioeconomic, logistical, and healthcare system-related issues. Addressing these constraints necessitates a multimodal approach, including increased access to telemedicine and strengthening healthcare infrastructure in resource-constrained settings.

This study's strength is its assessment of the healthcare-seeking behaviors of persons with chronic conditions who visited consultants' clinics prior to (2019), during (2020), and after the COVID-19 pandemic (2021). Previous research concentrated on clinic utilization immediately before and after treatment in various places around the world. The limitations of this study include recollection bias in determining the precise number of clinic visits missed, and the missed appointments were not based on hospital records. Respondents were required to provide a history of their clinic visits. Future research that use a prospective cohort study design can improve on this. Furthermore, because an

interviewer-administered questionnaire was utilized to gather data, there is an increased chance of social desirability bias, which may have influenced the result variables. Objective measures, such as evaluating hospital records for real-time data and conducting exit clinic interviews, should be examined in future study on the subject.

Conclusion

Patients with chronic illnesses who attended follow-up clinics missed much more clinic visits in 2020 (at the peak of the COVID-19 epidemic) than in previous years, as evidenced by the number of clinic visits missed. The most prevalent reasons for missing clinics in 2020 were COVID-19 restrictions, fear of contracting COVID-19, and a lack of transportation. It is therefore recommended that telemedicine and other technological advancements be implemented as treatment models in substitution for face-to-face consultations, which may be impractical during outbreak controls involving restriction measures that limit access to care for patients with chronic illnesses.

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Ethical approval: The Ethical Review Committee of UIITH, Ilorin provided ethical permission (ERC PAN/2022/08/0328) prior to the study's start.

Consent: All study participants provided informed permission after being introduced and explained the goal of the investigation. All received information was kept strictly secret. The study participants were informed of their right to withdraw their permission at any point during the trial.

Authors' contributions: TMA and MMF conceptualized the study. TMA, MMF, and OA designed it. ORA, TGK, MOA, and IAA gathered the data. OA examined the data, while ORA, TGK, MOA, MAJ, IAA, and TMA interpreted it. All authors contributed to and approved the final paper.

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